

Online appendix

Survey questions for the research paper “What prevents Finnish women from applying to software engineering roles? A preliminary analysis of survey data” by Annika Wolff, Antti Knutas, and Paula Savolainen.

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Survey questions

Section 1 - Attitudes towards women in software programming roles

We would like you to rate how much you agree with the following statements.

Rating scale:

Please rate on a scale of 1 - 7. Where 1 means ‘Not at all true’ and 7 means ‘Exactly true’

Cognitive component (current knowledge)

- COG1 It is easier for men to get software programming roles than women in Finland
- COG2 There are more men than women in software programming roles in Finland
- COG3 There are many opportunities in Finland for people with software programming skills
- COG4 Employers find it hard to find suitable candidates for some software programming roles

Affective component (their feeling about software programming and womens options)

- AFF1 I feel anxious about using computers and other technologies
- AFF2 I am concerned about the lack of opportunities for women in software programming roles
- AFF3 I enjoy learning new software programming and computing skills
- AFF4 If I saw a software programming role advertised that I was qualified for I would feel confident in applying for it

Behavioural component (their actions, or intended actions, towards software programming)

- BEC1 I intend to learn new software programming skills
- BEC2 I intend to apply for software programming roles in the future
- BEC3 If I saw a software programming role advertised that I was qualified for I would apply for it
- BEC4 I would recommend female friends to apply for software programming roles

Section 2 - self efficacy

General self-efficacy

- GS1 I can always manage to solve difficult problems if I try hard enough.
- GS2 If someone opposes me, I can find the means and ways to get what I want.
- GS3 It is easy for me to stick to my aims and accomplish my goals.
- GS4 I am confident that I could deal efficiently with unexpected events.
- GS5 Thanks to my resourcefulness, I know how to handle unforeseen situations.
- GS6 I can solve most problems if I invest the necessary effort.
- GS7 I can remain calm when facing difficulties because I can rely on my coping abilities.
- GS8 When I am confronted with a problem, I can usually find several solutions.
- GS9 If I am in trouble, I can usually think of a solution.
- GS10 I can usually handle whatever comes my way.

Measuring Computing Self-Efficacy

“I can...”

- CE1 solve a computing task
- CE2 develop computer software
- CE3 write coding scripts using text-based normal code
- CE4 use visual drag and drop code
- CE5 relate coding scripts to visual code
- CE6 troubleshoot software problems/errors
- CE7 wire parts of a hardware system together
- CE8 troubleshoot hardware problems

Section 3 - personal experiences

Open-ended questions

- EX1 Do you use a computer at: (tick all that apply)
 - Work
 - Home
 - Other (please specify) _____
- EX2 What activities do you do with a computer (either at work or home)
 - Graphic Design
 - Music
 - Art
 - Games
 - Using the internet
 - Word processing
 - Data analysis
 - Programming

- Other (please specify)
- EX3 If applicable, what programming, scripting or data analysis languages and tools are you confident in using? List all that you can think of
- EX4 Do you currently work in a software programming role?
- EX5 Have you in the past worked in a software programming role?
- EX6 Are you actively looking for a software programming role. If yes, please give details of the type of work you are looking for.
- EX7 Do you think that in the future you would be interested in applying for a software programming role
- EX 8 What do you think are the challenges of obtaining a software programming role?
- EX9 What do you think are the benefits of obtaining a software programming role?
- EX10 Have you ever had a negative experience in applying for a software programming role. If yes, please describe your experience
- EX11 Do you think that women face barriers in software programming roles more than men. If yes, why do you think this is?
- EX12 How would you improve the career opportunities for women in software programming? Please list all ideas
- EX13 Have you ever faced barriers, or know someone that has faced barriers, in pursuing a career in software programming? Please describe
- EX14 At school, were there equal opportunities for girls and boys to use technology and do software programming? Please explain your answer
- EX15 At school, did you feel supported to study technology-based subjects? Please explain your answer
- EX16 At school, did you feel comfortable making subject choices that would support a career in software programming? Please explain your answer
- EX17 Were there any technology-related clubs at school and if so, did you participate and was it easy to take part? Please explain your answer.
- EX18 Is there anything else you would like to tell us that wasn't covered in this survey?

Demographic Questions

This survey is completely anonymous and cannot be used to identify you in any way. The following demographic questions will help in the interpretation of results, however they are optional. If you prefer not to answer, please leave blank.

Please indicate your age category:

- 17 or younger
- 18-20
- 21-29
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50-59
- 60 or older

What is your gender?

- Female
- Male
- Other (specify)

What is the highest degree or level of school you have completed? (If you're currently undertaking study, please indicate the highest degree you have *received*.) ** I have finished school up to age: (16/18)

- High school degree (or equivalent)
- Vocational degree
- University degree (e.g. BA, BSc)
- Master's degree (e.g. MA, MS, MEd)
- Professional degree
- Doctorate (e.g. PhD, EdD)

What is your current employment status?

- Employed full time (35 or more hours per week)
- Employed part time (up to 35 hours per week)
- Self-employed
- Unemployed and currently looking for work
- Not employed and not currently looking for work (e.g. homemaker)
- Student
- Retired
- Other (please specify) _____

Which region of Finland do you live in? _____

Would you describe your area as:

Village

Town

Other (please specify) _____

Would you describe your area as:

Rural

Semi-rural

Suburban

Urban

Which region of Finland did you spend the majority of your high school years?

Would you describe this area as:

Village

Town

Other (please specify) _____

Would you describe this area as:

Rural

Semi-rural

Suburban

Urban